
Impact of Code Switching on ESL Learners during Pandemic at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Rahim Yar Khan Campus

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of code switching on ESL learners specifically during pandemic situation. The population was the language teachers of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Rahim Yar Khan. The basic focus of the study was to find out the advantages that teachers achieved through code switching in ESL classrooms during pandemic. It tried to find out that how code switching is efficient to increase the learning proficiency among the ESL learners. Actually COVID-19 added to the sufferings of world and caused immeasurable loss. After health the greatest loss was observed in the field of education. This pandemic slowed down the pace of learning by creating a lot of hurdles in the way of gaining knowledge. Physical classes were extinct and online system was new for the learners and instructors both. In the present era, a good number of educational institutions in Pakistan have declared that the language of instruction in the classrooms should be English, which is the chief second language in the country. When a language user jumps from one language to another language, this process is called code switching. This technique is widely used in Pakistani classrooms. It is believed to be beneficial to switch from one code to another in an ESL class. Sociolinguistics measures code-switching not only as a constituent of communal social life but surrounds the societal strata of speakers' linguistic difference, societal variables, and societal settings. Seemingly language teachers deliberately choose code switching for the promotion, comprehension, and improvement of second language (L2) learning. This paper puts light on the advantages of code switching on the track of language learning, investigates a few strands of code switching and then its efficacy in developing L2 knowledge amongst the students at The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Rahim Yar Khan Campus. The findings of the study make clear that the code-switching causes learning sessions connected and it facilitates the learners to switch from L2 to L1. It can be implied that code-switching has a strong impact on language teaching.

Keywords: Code switching, ESL, Sociolinguistics, Second Language Learning,

1. Introduction

Pakistan is believed to be one of the largest multilingual countries having speaker of not less than sixty expressions in various areas of the country. The first language of Pakistan is Urdu (L1) and the second language is English (L2). Abbasian & Khajavi (2011) are of the view that English has been the widely used foreign language in the teaching of various subjects in educational institutions like schools, universities, and different language schools. In Pakistani educational institutes, teachers tend to code-switch between Urdu and English language in order to make concepts clear for students as books are generally written in English language and mother tongue is generally Urdu, Punjabi, Siraiki, Pushto or Sindhi. The Islamia

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University of Bahawalpur is an example of such bilingual institute.

By the end of 2019, COVID-19 has set its claws in the whole world and has caused destruction in the lives of people and affected their health. With increasing challenges related to health and life, many countries have adapted various measures to lessen the effect of pandemic COVID-19. These measures include quarantine, social distancing, online teaching mode, hybrid teaching mode and so on.

Online teaching method is also used in The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. With students coming from various linguistic backgrounds and having different mother tongues, it becomes necessary for instructors of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur to code-switch between English and Urdu language. It helps in more clarity of concepts, better attention of students, acquisition of focused language and to reinforce the lesson stuff. Focusing on these encouraging viewpoints, this research discusses the advantages gained after the use of code-switching in the classrooms of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The researchers specified some areas where code switching may provide support in learning English as second language. Having weaker English basis the students of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur sometimes feel blank to grab the linguistics concepts. Grammatical concepts are often difficult for them so code switching is sometimes helpful in teaching those particular students. They feel reluctant to communicate in English. The procedure of Code-switching can be helpful in linguistic class to help learners overcome communication problem (Zabrodskaia, 2007). The motives why code switching is done depend on multiple reasons such as time management, syllabus completion, clarity of concepts and so on.

2. Literature Review:

“Bilingual or multilingual speakers utilize code-switching to combine two or more languages in a single verbal exchange.” (Bailey, 1999). Code-switching is useful to transfer information in multiple languages without changing the meaning. Jakobsson and Rydén (2010) believe that speakers opt for code-switching according to situation as per their needs. Meyerhoff, Schleaf et al. (2015) observed that speakers who can speak more than one language understand that sometimes one language of variety is more efficient in conveying the meaning as compared to other.

Code-switching is used by bilingual speakers. It is a difficult and rule-governed process according to Heredia and Altarriba (2001). As a matter of fact, code-switching is an intellectual activity instead of the traditional view of a less educated area (Algarin-Ruiz, 2014).

According to Modupeola (2013), for teachers there is no need to spend their time clarifying things to their students and looking for the easiest terms to clear up the misunderstandings. Thus, in his opinion code-switching is a useful instrument tool in classroom settings.

Simasiku, Kasanda et al. (2015) also believe code-switching to be useful tool for efficient teaching and effective learning. Modupeola (2013) said that this method makes teachers enable to hit equilibrium between the subject of particular contact and the language use. The previous knowledge of student can be utilized by teacher to make the L2 comprehensible.

To reveal specific characteristics, generate particular meanings, and assist specific interpersonal relationships code-switching is used (Gudykunst 2004). It comprises of changing of sentences and phrases L1 and L2 and also switching in a long narrative (Musleh, Ibrahim et al. 2020). Sert (2005) states, When dealing with specific grammar points, this

(code-switching) is most commonly witnessed in grammar training, where the teacher considers the mother tongue of his students to set the language.

Shafi, Kazmi et al. (2020) suggested code-switching as a vital teaching and communicative technique. According to them most of the time among bilingual learners opt for code-switching. Gulzar (2010) figured out that in language classrooms technique of code-switching is used to help the students. He states, “Students' needs can be met through code swapping. As a result, it is strongly advised that code-switching be used as a strategy..(Becker, 2001)”.

Above mentioned facts gathered from various studies paved a strong foundation for the present study. Timely implementation and right context is necessary for accurate code-switching.

3. Research Objective

The major goal of study was:

To find out the impact of Code Switching on ESL learners during the pandemic.

4. Research Question

The gap which this study is trying to fill is mentioned below:

What is the impact of Code Switching on ESL Learners during the pandemic?

5. Research Methodology:

The current research is mixed in nature. The researchers obtained the data by asking questions from the relevant persons to find out why language teachers code swap and whether they believe it is a useful approach in the complicated environment of ESL learners' classrooms. In mixed studies scholars can use both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to talk about things they don't understand or perceive. The Language teachers from The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Rhaim Yar Khan Campus make up the population. The sample is chosen from the population using the Convenient Sampling technique. It is a kind of non-random and non-sampling technique in which the participants are chosen on ease to meet the objectives of this study. The specific conditions are met, such as geographic closeness, ease of access at a specific instance, simple accessibility, or a willingness to assist. One of the basic examples of convenient sampling is the students of the university. The participants of the study were chosen from a pool of 10 English teachers on campus. Data was obtained using questionnaire, having five questions, which gave participants a good amount of leeway to react in a more useful way while still allowing them to provide enough data with only a few questions.

6. Data Analysis

6.1 Qualitative analysis

In response to question number one majority of teachers has strongly approved that code switching is instinctive and cataleptic habit that is also a situation-oriented activity. One of the teachers answered, “Surely situations encourage code switching because sometimes difficult concepts demand more clarifications and L1 facilitates the learners to grab the concepts efficiently”.

In response to question number 2, most of the teachers agreed that code-switching can save

time during language teaching. Thus, it can be deduced that most of the time students are not able to understand instructions and basic concepts if only L2 is used. With the help of code-switching, time is saved if teachers use students' L1. Learners having less command in L2 remain confused if instructions are given only in L2. As a teacher shared, "Code-switching is a careful time-saving strategy employed by teachers for quality teaching and learning."

As far as question number 3 is concerned, a good number of teachers agreed that code-switching is a beneficial teaching technique in ESL classrooms especially you have. They favored that code switching that is bilingual is a helpful technique employed for language teaching. Thus, in a nutshell, the use of teacher-student code switching in the classroom enhances the cognitive abilities and understanding of students.

For question number 4, teachers supported the idea that learners' perception level is enhanced with the use of code-switching. Students with low proficiency in L2 need code switching often to build the linguistic concepts. On the other hand, the elevated skill learners are relentless and favored that Target language must be the teaching method, although learners having weak proficiency level in L2 require provisions from the L1. It has been found out by the researchers of the study that L1 is more helpful in language learning process than L2.

While answering question number 5, maximum number of teachers assumed that the code switching plays a vital role in the comprehension of grammatical conventions of the TL. A participant stated, Resemblance among different syntactic structures of various languages help in grabbing the grammatical concepts. According to one participant, there is no disgrace in confessing that students always feel shy while communicating in foreign language. So, code-switching is helpful in teaching various grammatical concepts to students.

7. Quantitative Analysis

Tool used for quantitative analysis of the current study is questionnaire. However, several specific terms related to linguistics (such as ESL, code-switching) were used in the questionnaires. Thus, researchers thought it mandatory to clarify the meanings of those terms and explain the scope of whole questionnaire to the sample.

8. Question Wise Analysis

Analysis of questions included for the current study is given below.

Q.1: Do you think certain situations encourage code-switching in ESL classroom? If yes, then kindly explain how.

Chart 1: Quantitative Analysis of question number 1

As far as question number 1 is concerned, 90 percent of the teachers agreed that under certain circumstances or situations, such as online lectures or students belonging from backward/Urdu medium backgrounds, the use of code-switching becomes more important. Just 10 percent of the teachers disagreed. Thus, it can be concluded that some particular situations require more use of code-switching.

Q.2: Do you feel that a teacher can save time during language teaching through code-switching?

Chart 2: Quantitative Analysis of question number 2

As shown in the above figure, 70 percent of the teachers agreed that code-switching can help a teacher in saving time during language learning. 20 percent of the teachers disagreed from above statement and 10 per cent of the teachers remained neutral and gave no stance. In a nutshell, it can be interpreted from the above analysis that a teacher can teach more material in less time by using the technique of code-switching in classrooms.

Q.3: Do you think code-switching is beneficial for teaching in ESL classrooms? If yes, then explain how.

Chart 3: Quantitative Analysis of question number 3

According to chart number 3, 70 percent of the teachers agreed with the statement that code-switching is beneficial for teaching in ESL classrooms as it helps the students to learn more efficiently from their native language to second language. 10 percent of the teachers disagreed from the above-mentioned statement and 20 percent of the teachers remained neutral. Thus, it is more conceivable to say that code-switching helps the teachers during teaching in ESL classrooms.

Q.4: Do you agree that code-switching improves the level of linguistic perception in students? If yes then kindly explain your stance.

Chart 4: Quantitative Analysis of question number 4

As mentioned in above figure, 80 percent of the teachers agreed with the statement that code-switching help in improving the linguistic perception of students or learners. However, 20 percent of the teachers disagreed from the above mentioned question. Thus, it can be concluded from the above discussion that code-switching is beneficial for the learners and helps them in improving their linguistic perception.

Q.5: Do you think code-switching helps in grabbing the grammatical concepts?

Chart 5: A Quantitative Analysis of question number 5

While answering question number 5, 90 percent of the teachers agreed with the above-mentioned statement. Just 10 percent of the teachers disagreed from the above-mentioned statement. Thus, by keeping in mind these figures, it is possible to say that code-switching is helpful for the students in grabbing various grammatical concepts and it is also beneficial for the teachers to teacher different grammatical concepts to the students.

9. Analysis in tabular form

Quantitative analysis in the form of table of the questionnaire is given below:

	Agree	Disagree	Neutral
Question 1	90%	10%	___
Question 2	70%	20%	10%
Question 3	70%	10%	20%
Question 4	80%	20%	___
Question 5	90%	10%	___

Table 1: Analysis in the form of table

10. Results and Discussion

From above analysis, it can be implied that most teachers of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Rahim Yar Khan Campus agreed with the point that code-switching has a strong impact on language teaching. Various situations, such as online lectures, require teachers to adopt the method of code-switching as sometimes during online lectures students do not have strong network connections which results in low level of understanding if only targeted language is used. Many times, teachers want to save time and cover material in less time. In such cases, code-switching is also useful. At the beginning of learning English language, many students do not have strong command on English language. They feel more comfortable to use their mother languages in the beginning. Thus, for teaching in ESL classrooms at early stages, in some cases teachers find it easy to use the technique of code-switching. Certain linguistic concepts can be made clear to the students if technique of code-switching is used. In this way, teachers can relate the concepts with students' norms and values. Grammatical concepts, such as tenses, parts of speech can be better taught if the technique of code-switching is used. Students use proper and accurate grammar in their native languages but find it difficult to use correct grammar in second language. So, if the technique of code-switching is used teachers can help the students to learn various grammatical concepts in much easier way. Hence, it is conceivable to say that code-switching can have a strong impact on language teaching during COVID-19 if used appropriately as online lectures, hybrid teaching is the need of time now and students feel more comfortable if some words or phrases are used in their native language during language teaching.

11. Conclusion

At The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, RYK campus, the study focused on instructors' use of code-switching in ESL classrooms during pandemic situations, finding it to be a useful tool for language education. It emphasized the fact that code-switching is a universally observed phenomenon. The results show that the teacher's positive attitudes towards code-switching have been consistently supported through all the data. During online mode it helped the learners to gain the concepts. The selected teachers opined that L1 regulates the flow of learning L2 especially in the sub campus of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur where the learners come from backward areas having weaker linguistic basics.

12. Recommendation

he further quantitative study can be conducted to find out the harms of code switching in ESL learning class during pandemic situation.

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